

THE USE OF BITUMEN-EMULSION COMPOSITES IN ROAD CONSTRUCTION OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN.

Abdikadirov Polat Urazimbetovich

senior lecturer.

Allanazarov Sharibay Bekanovich

senior lecturer.

Republic of Uzbekistan, Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Karakalpak State University, Nukus.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13284599>

Summary: The article presents. Device for treating road surfaces, using thin-layer coatings, preparing stable bitumen emulsions.

Key words: protective road surfaces, bitumen emulsions containing Ca O in mineral lime powder.

To ensure the safety of vehicles on high-category roads, it is necessary to have high protective layers of road surfaces. The top layers of the road surface ensure the smoothness and roughness required, and protect the road surface from the penetration of water into the road surface.

Stops destruction and extends the service life of old coatings that have shown signs of wear in the form of cracks, peeling, chipping, and others. When installed on crushed stone and gravel surfaces, it provides dust removal and significantly more comfortable driving conditions for vehicles.

Surface finishing is a method of creating a rough coating surface and installing wear layers and protective layers by pouring a thin layer of organic binder onto the base, spreading high-grade crushed stone and compacting it. The main work includes pouring bitumen, distributing and compacting crushed stone. The process of final formation of surface treatment lasts about 10 days

Surface treatment performs the following functions:

- Restores and improves the adhesion qualities of the road surface;
- Forms a wear layer and a protective layer against water penetration into road clothing;
- Stops destruction and extends the service life of old coatings that show signs of wear in the form of cracks, peeling, chipping, and others;

The production of high-quality bitumen emulsions is difficult without the use of surfactants that have the necessary emulsifying properties. Many chemicals are used to emulsify bitumen emulsions, but in economic and technological terms only some of them are widely used. The action of the emulsifier is to create a good structural shell of crushed bitumen droplets that do not burst when they

meet. Bitumen's, being non-polar substances, do not dissolve in polar liquid-water.

Therefore, they can be mixed with water only to form a colloidal disperse system - emulsions. The formation and stability of the emulsion is achieved by introducing special emulsifiers into it. Surfactants or finely dispersed solid powders due to surfactants used as an emulsifier, bitumen road emulsions are divided into anionic (EBA) and cationic (EBC).

What is an emulsifier in simple words?

Emulsifiers are chemical compounds or mixtures that allow the formation of an emulsion that is stable over time. The role of the emulsifier is to create stable micelles that form at the water-oil interface.

Emulsification is the process of mixing at least two difficult-to-mix liquids. The most difficult task of emulsification is the crushing of the dispersed phase into small droplets.

Surfactant molecules consist of polar and non-polar parts, which are directed at the bitumen-water interface. The molecules are non-polar part facing the bitumen, and the polar part is facing water. In this position, the surfactants reduce the surface tension at their interface. Bitumen (phase) and water (medium). Due to the separation of the polar group of the surfactant, the phase particles acquire an electrical charge (positive with a cationic emulsifier, negative with an anionic emulsifier). Single charged particles of the phase repel, which prevents them from sticking together and makes the emulsion more stable. Mineral emulsifiers adhere to bitumen particles and form protective shells at the interface between them and water that prevent connection.

To prepare road emulsions, finely ground mineral substances are used, as well as water-soluble organic emulsifiers.

Emulsions with cationic active emulsifiers are called acidic with anionic emulsifiers alkaline. The content of mineral emulsifiers in the emulsion usually does not exceed 5-20% and depends on the dispersion, and the content of water-soluble emulsifiers in the emulsion is 3%. Resin organic acids, alkaline naphthenic salts, cotton tar, and second fat tar are used as anionic emulsifiers.

Active cation emulsifiers include finely ground powders of lime, cement, limestone, carbonate, coal, etc. Depending on the content and properties of emulsifiers, the amount of bitumen, two types of emulsions can be obtained: direct, when drops of bitumen are dispersed in water, and reverse, when water is dispersed in bitumen. In the road industry, direct emulsions are mainly used. When emulsions interact with mineral material due to the adsorption of the

emulsifier, absorption and evaporation of water, the balance of the system is destroyed and its disintegration occurs. The decomposition of road bitumen emulsion composites depends on the type of emulsifier and the ambient temperature. The rate and degradation characteristics of bitumen emulsion composites can be controlled by introducing the desired additives. The stability of emulsions with anionic emulsifiers is $\text{PH}=7\text{...}11$, active cation 3..7. With increasing pH, the stability of cation-active emulsions decreases, and that of anion-active emulsions increases. Determination of PH is carried out by introducing salt and acid or alkali into the emulsion of materials. By treating mineral materials with cement and lime, it improves the adhesion of the binder to stone materials.

Preparation of emulsion composite bitumen uses viscous bitumen grades from BND 200/300 to BND 40/60, depending on the climatic conditions of the construction site and the type of road pavement. An emulsifier is added to bitumen or water. The finished components of the emulsion composite are stored in special containers, from which they are supplied to the emulsion installation. In an emulsion installation, with the help of rotating blades, bitumen is crushed (dispersed) in an aqueous environment. The emulsifier is adsorbed on the surface of bitumen particles and gives stability to the resulting emulsion. During the production of emulsions, aqueous solutions of the emulsifier (when the emulsifier is introduced into bitumen) are heated to a temperature of $70 \dots 90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. When preparing mineral emulsifiers, paddle mixers are used. First, water is introduced into the installation at a temperature of about 90°C , then the required amount of finely ground emulsifiers is added. All these materials are mixed well until a homogeneous creamy mass is obtained at a temperature of about $70\text{-}80^\circ\text{C}$, after which hot bitumen is gradually introduced into the solution. The entire mixture is mixed well in a mixer until a homogeneous mixture is obtained, easily diluted with water.

In regulating the structural properties of bitumen emulsions, the main role belongs to mineral powder. Combining with bitumen, the filler forms a double system "Mineral powder bitumen". For many years it was assumed that the purpose of mineral powder in bitumen emulsions was limited to filling voids, that is, ensuring the required density. While studying the literature on the purpose of mineral powder in asphalt concrete, many researchers gave great importance to the role of mineral powder in asphalt concrete. The finely crushed material is not just a void filler - it acts as a complement to the bitumen binder. The introduction of mineral powder improves the quality of emulsions with fine

crushing of all mineral material. As a result, the multiplication of the number of points of contact between particles increases the strength of the asphalt concrete road surface.

Bitumen emulsions are liquid bitumen dispersed (crushed) in water with the addition of an emulsifier in the form of surfactants. The main parameters are the work ability of substances. The main parameters of the work-ability of wear layers are the stability of the structure, due to the adhesion of bitumen to the mineral filler, bending strength, resistance of the structure to changes in moisture and temperature (periodic freezing and thawing) conditions, fatigue failure, and others. It is known that the destruction of road pavements when water penetrates into the structure of the material occurs due to a change in the pore space, that is, its increase, resulting in a breakdown of the bonds between binders (bitumen) and mineral materials due to the stresses that arise when water penetrates the pores. Water under the influence of pore pressure has an explosive effect on the pores, destroying the material. The use of bitumen emulsion wearing layers should reduce the penetration of moisture into pavements.

The solution to the issue of regulating the structural and mechanical properties of bitumen emulsions depends on the bitumen and mineral material. An important role in the processes of structure formation of bitumen emulsions belongs to the mineral powder included in the composition of the composite [4,21,37,38]

Combining with "bitumen, mineral powder" it is noted [36-37,57-58] that at a certain ratio of bitumen-mineral powder, the highest strength of the structured disperse system is achieved, forming with these materials. As a result, the resistance of bitumen to impact loads increases, the density of the resulting mass increases, and the strength under shear and compression stresses increases, and fragility decreases. Mineral powders make it possible to regulate deformation and reduce subsidence of road surfaces. When filling bitumen with mineral powder, the viscosity of the mixture increases and heat resistance increases. A traditional powder with a large number of positive adsorption centres' and high structuring ability is limestone mineral powder [4]. Research work has found that the best are mineral powders obtained by fine grinding of limestone and dolomite. Almost everyone comes to this conclusion. Researchers working in this area [17,49-50,68]. To find the possibility of using such bitumen powders-mineral mixtures without deteriorating their properties, it is necessary

to understand the mechanism of interaction between the mineral powder and the organic binder (bitumen).

An analysis of literature sources on the use of lime in road construction for the preparation of bitumen emulsions made it possible to establish that lime (fluff, boiling powder) and cement are considered effective and affordable mineral powders [30,85]. According to data [4,30], when the fluff lime activator is introduced into bitumen, not only better wetting and adhesion of the bitumen is achieved, but also its faster mixing with wet mineral material.

In the process of research, the authors of [142] proved that by adding slaked lime to bitumen, the adhesion of the mineral powder to the binder can be improved. Also, the addition of a water molecule to lime molecules can form a crystallization structure. Based on this, it can be assumed that when asphalt concrete pavements containing lime in the composition of mineral powder are saturated with water, physical and chemical processes will occur in the body of the composite.

Associated with the hydration of lime, leading to the formation of a stable structure. And further, it will entail an improvement in the quality, durability and performance properties of asphalt concrete in road pavement.

Bibliography:

- 1 Volkov M.I., Borsh I.M. Research of mineral powders for asphalt concrete Proceedings of HADI-1956 issue 18. pp. 12-17.
2. Traxler R.N. Asphalt. Its Composition Properties and Uses-New-York Reinhold 1961-37p.
- 3 Peterson J.C., Ensley E.K., Barbour F.A. Molecular interaction of asphalt in the asphalt-aggregate interrace-region/Trans. Res 1974-No.515. -P. 67-68.
- 4 Zolotarev V.A. Features of wetting the surface of stone materials with bitumen // Izvestia vuzov. Construction and architecture. -L991. -No. 8. -WITH. 68-70.
- 5 Lisikhina A.Ts. The use of surfactants and other additives in the construction of asphalt concrete and similar coatings. -M: Motor transport, 1957-56s.
- 6 Khudyakova T.S. Influence of mineral material on the adhesive strength of bitumen-mineral mixtures // Chemistry and technology of fuels and oils. -1990. -No. 12. -p.28-29.
7. Rybyeva T.G. Study of the influence of the mineralogical composition of powders on the structural and mechanical properties of bitumen-mineral materials: Author's abstract. dis... cand. tech. nauk.-M., 1960. - 18 p.
8. Rebinder P.A. Surfactants.- M.: Knowledge, 1961.-46 p.
9. Ambros R.A. On the study of the effect of chemical additives on

FRANCE

MODELS AND METHODS IN MODERN SCIENCE

International scientific-online conference

FRANCE

adhesion of bitumen to stone materials // Tr. Tallinn Polytechnic Institute: -
Estonian Publishing House. - 1956. - Series A. -
No. 69.-S. 74-77.

